

MEDICAL ADVERTISING IN SOCIOPRAGMATIC ASPECT**Sobirova Dilnoza Rasulovna**

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Abstract. This article deals with the issue of researching medical advertisements from an anthropocentric point of view. The main focus is on the basics of sociopragmatic research. The issue of the role of sociopragmatics in linguistics is also covered.

Key words: anthropocentrism, sociopragmatics, medical advertising, addressee.

Introduction

As time passes, science develops, and research based on new paradigms takes the place of practical research. Naturally, this process also applies in linguistics. Language phenomena have been studied from the point of view of comparative-historical linguistics since the time of ancient Indian linguistics. ... and on the basis of Ferdinand de Saussure's teaching on structuralism, a new system-structural direction appeared. ... The functionalization of linguistic tools, the process of speech communication and the study of issues related to the context and speech activity prompted the emergence of anthropocentric theory [1, 8-9]. The word "anthropocentrism" comes from the Greek "anthrropos" - man + Latin. "centrum" - the center. In linguistics: approach to language from the perspective of the human factor; It is the main principle of language research in such fields as

linguo-culturology, cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, ethnopsycholinguistics, intercultural communication, neurolinguistics [2, 21]. The formation of the anthropocentric paradigm is related to the research of the factor of the speaker - the owner of the language. In world linguistics, the study of the language system from an anthropocentric point of view is mainly manifested in studies related to a number of fields such as cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, pragmalinguistics, sociolinguistics, linguoculturology. According to the authors of the manual "Lingvopersonology - an independent field of linguistics", although the research on linguistic semantics, pragmalinguistics, and cognitive linguistics in Uzbek linguistics shows tendencies of an anthropocentric direction, the research in this regard is insufficient [4, 21]. .

Material and Methods.

Pragmalinguistics is a new direction of scientific and practical research of human linguistic activity, and today its place in the system of scientific knowledge is being firmly established in Uzbek linguistics. According to Sh. Safarov, one of the pioneers of this direction, the "girls" of pragmalinguistics, a number of researches are also emerging in new directions such as ethnopragmatics, sociopragmatics, ethnosociopragmatics, intercultural pragmatics, and comparative pragmatics. The formation of sociopragmatics is associated with the name of a number of linguists such as J. Leach, G. Kasper, P. Brown, S. Levinson, J. Yule. In a special treatise dedicated to the principle of respect published by P. Brown and S. Levinson in 1987, the slogan "Sociolinguistics should be applied to pragmatics" was put forward [5,106].

Results

Although the research methods of sociopragmatics and pragmalinguistics are

very similar, they are not different names of the same direction. The authors of "The Cambridge Handbook Of Sociopragmatics" attempt to explain the similarities and differences between sociopragmatics and pragmalinguistics through a diagram based on J. Leach's research. [3, 4] (1-figure).

Figure 1. Difference between pragmalinguistics and sociopragmatics

It can be said that sociopragmatics was formed at the intersection of sociolinguistics, which studies the speaker in relation to society, and pragmalinguistics, which directly studies the use of language by the participants of communication.

Discussion

Sociolinguistics deals with the systematic linguistic correlation of relatively fixed and stable social variables (for example, a person's region of origin, ethnicity, social class, gender, age) in the way a person usually speaks. On the other hand, pragmatics is mainly concerned with describing the linguistic correlation of relatively variable characteristics of a person (for example, relative position, social role) and the way a speaker uses his (social) linguistic repertoire to achieve a certain goal. Sociolinguistics is static and offers a "snapshot" of the language of a

given society at a given time. Pragmatics is dynamic, it describes what the addressee from the community will do with these resources, how he will use them to change the situation or maintain the status quo. Pragmatics is related to sociolinguistics and takes a sociolinguistic description of a person's ability to use language as a starting point: sociolinguistics tells us what linguistic resources a person has, pragmatics shows how linguistic resources can be used. The authors of the textbook "Fundamentals of Pragmalinguistics" intended for students of higher educational institutions are M. Hakimov and M. Gaziyeva. they note that it will be done.

Jonathan Culpeper, a scientist at Lancaster University in the United Kingdom, notes that sociopragmatics is more on the social side of pragmatics than on the linguistic side. Sociopragmatics focuses on the construction and understanding of meanings arising from interactions between language (or other semiotic resources) and socio-cultural phenomena. It refers to interactions at the central level, especially local, meso-level contexts (eg, patterns, speech act (activity) types, genres). It examines the norms that often emerge in such contexts, how they are used by actors, and how they lead to assessments of appropriateness. Thus, the scope of research topics of sociopragmatics can be defined as follows:

1. Addressee-communication-addressee.
2. Communicative intention.
3. Speech act.

Anthropocentric linguistics focuses on the human factor. From the point of view of this linguistics, when "man" enters into a communicative relationship, he appears in different positions. In one place, he acts as a provider of information, in another place as a receiver of information, and in another place, for a third person,

they play the role of communication participants in a general sense. Communicants are the participants of communication in Lingvopersonology; informant - addressee, communicator; the recipient of information is studied under terms such as addressee, recipient. D. Mamirova, a scientist engaged in the study of sociolinguistic features of advertising, in her research, the addressee in advertising is a person familiar with the advertising text, a reader, in addition, in the field of advertising, the recipient (lat. recipient - to be accepted, ing. recipient) is a certain social stratum. The term member, those who receive oral or written information from the respondent is also used in this sense. It is noted that the addressee is the entity that prepares and distributes the advertising text. In this regard, it is appropriate to call the creators (providers) of advertising as addressees, and the receivers of advertising (readers, listeners, viewers) as addressees.

The following issues can be systematically investigated in our study, which is devoted to the illumination of the sociopragmatic features of medical advertisements:

- 1) communicative intent in medical advertisements.
- 2) speech act in medical advertisements.
- 3) addressee and addressee factor in medical advertisements (methods of influencing the addressee, motives, socio-demographic and psychographic characteristics of addressees).

F.P. The dictionary-reference dedicated to explaining the main concepts of journalism, advertising, public relations (see "public relations", "public relations", "public relations"), created by a team of authors headed by Nasterenko, contains the main methods of advertising research. The following are noted as directions:

1. Study of consumer characteristics.

2. Product analysis.
3. Market research.
4. Analysis of possible channels of communication.
5. Research the effectiveness of decisions in the field of advertising.

Conclusion

Our research corresponds to the directions of 1. Research of consumer characteristics and 2. Analysis of possible channels of communication provided for in the dictionary. After all, in sociopragmatics, it is important to analyze the social characteristics of society members, as well as the specific aspects of communication.

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